

USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE COURSE OF PRACTICAL TRAINING FOR ECONOMICS MAJORS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION: The characteristics of effective digital technology use in teaching economic sciences to aspiring economists in technical higher education institutions were examined in this work.

KEYWORDS: professional activity, higher education, digital educational technologies, and efficient educational technologies.

Introduction. In order to accomplish this goal, the following tasks must be put into practice: evaluate the fundamentals of efficient digital technologies for teaching economic sciences in technical higher education institutions; ascertain the function and significance of efficient digital technologies in higher education's educational process; The aim of this study is to examine the efficient use of digital technologies in the field of "Econometrics" and to formulate suggestions and ideas for the systematic enhancement of the use of these technologies in the teaching of economic sciences in higher education. The focus of the study is on the social relationships that arise when economic science courses in technical higher education institutions employ efficient digital technologies. Effective digital technologies for teaching economic sciences in higher education are the focus of this study.

Presently, a nation's ability to compete internationally is largely determined by the caliber of its human capital. This is the reason why educational establishments all over the world are creating useful educational technologies. The roles of the teacher (the informant is replaced by the consultant role) and the student (the information does not play the role of the teacher) are also significantly altered by effective digital educational technologies that are based on student activation. In professional education, the role of the teacher is to create the conditions necessary for students to take initiative. The teacher's activity takes the place of the students' activity.

Methods and Materials. Today, the following questions lie in the education system: "How to teach?", "What to teach?". Consequently, in the conditions of state educational standards, students really become the central figure of the educational process, forcing higher educational institutions to organize the educational process not as learning, but as knowledge. Changes in the conditions and nature of the professional activity of graduates of technical higher education institutions inevitably lead to the need to improve their educational processes using digital technologies. It allows us to prepare a graduate of higher education for systematic actions in a professional situation, work with a constantly growing stream of information, analyze and plan one's own activities, act in conditions of uncertainty, self-improvement (self-awareness, self-control, self-esteem, self-management and self-development), as well as creative self-

It expresses the desire to understand. To date, there are few scientific works devoted to the problems of effective use of digital technologies in the teaching of economic sciences in the educational system.

The process of teaching economic sciences in education under the conditions of the contemporary market economy necessitates a number of factors linked to the financial success of future economist graduates' employment, which in and of itself requires devoting resources from educational institutions. demands, which consequently has the tendency to minimize them. This leads to the issue that educators "tend to solve, including the use of modern, effective technologies of teaching economic sciences in higher education. "The topic of employing efficient technologies to teach economic sciences in higher education has come up more and more in recent years. These are related to the introduction of new teaching styles and methods as well as new approaches to the educational process, in addition to new technological tools. In higher education institutions, teaching technologies for economic sciences is a methodical approach to planning, executing, assessing, modifying, and then repeating the educational process in the process of teaching economic sciences.

Results. The strategies and resources a teacher uses to sway students are referred to as teaching technology. Educational technologies appeared at a certain stage of economic development of society and developed along with it.

Digital technology is a discrete system based on methods of encoding and transmitting information, which allows you to perform many different tasks in the shortest possible time. Effective digital technologies for the teaching of economic sciences in higher education institutions consist of three interrelated components: modern content (given to students, not the acquisition of scientific knowledge, but the development of issues relevant to modern business practice) includes), modern teaching methods (active methods of developing issues based not only on passive perception of the material, but also on student interaction and involvement in the learning process); modern educational infrastructure (they include informational, technological, organizational and communication components that allow effective use of the advantages of distance education).

One of the most significant developments in global education over the past ten years has been the integration of digital technologies into the teaching of economic sciences in higher education institutions. It is undeniable that the creation of new information technologies and their integration into the educational process "affects the development of the personality of a modern student studying economics and his perception of the world around him."

Games have a direct bearing on how immersive technologies are incorporated into the educational system. Through the use of "numbers," educational games in the economic sciences can be a fun way to "immerse students in the necessary economic environment" and experience complex problems as well as build intricate systems of interaction amongst economics students. Nevertheless, there are currently some restrictions on the ability to create an immersive learning environment for economic science courses in higher education institutions. Specifically, A.V. Zamkov makes a distinction between problems that are technical, economic, and psychophysical; at the technical level, "the limitations are very clear – the need for expensive workstations, special end devices, high-quality optics, and high-speed communication channels." These kinds of issues are prevalent in practically all developing technologies and are financially solvable.

Despite the problems identified with the new technology, it can be said with confidence that it will increasingly penetrate the educational processes of students of the digital generation and involve them emotionally.

Discussion. In the teaching of economic sciences in higher educational institutions, modern and effective digital technologies of economic sciences are used in the educational process to implement the student's knowledge and creative activity, which allows to improve the quality of education and "effective use of study time". will give.

The introduction of modern effective digital technologies into the educational process of teaching economic sciences allows the teacher to increase the depth and consistency of knowledge, to strengthen his skills in various fields of activity; development of technological thinking, the ability to independently plan educational and self-education activities; formation of skills to strictly comply with the requirements of technological discipline in the organization of training sessions on economic sciences in higher education. Utilizing an extensive array of efficacious digital technologies in the economic sciences curriculum at postsecondary educational establishments enables educators to optimize class duration and accomplish superior learning outcomes for pupils. Specialists' traditional training, which emphasized the development of scientific knowledge and skills, is falling more and more behind current demands. Academic subjects should not be the foundation of education; rather, contemporary methods of thinking and doing should. Not only must a highly qualified expert in the field of economics be found, but he must also be included in the training phase of the development of new, efficient technologies, adjusted to the demands of a particular production environment, and given the freedom to make his own decisions.

Effective digital technologies for teaching economic sciences create ample opportunities for differentiation and individualization of educational activities. The result of the effective use of digital technologies in the teaching of economic sciences in higher education depends to a lesser extent on the teacher's skills, and is determined by the sum of its components. Effective digital technologies for teaching economic sciences are related to increasing the effectiveness of teaching and learning, and the final result of the educational process is aimed at training highly qualified specialists in the field of economics using digital technologies. Based on the experience of effective use of digital technologies in the teaching of economic sciences, we can highlight some of their advantages: they help students learn active methods of acquiring new knowledge; provides an opportunity to acquire a high level of personal social activity; in the teaching of economic sciences, it creates conditions where students have no choice but to study; stimulates creative abilities of students; helps to bring the study closer to the practice of everyday life, forms not only knowledge and skills in science, but also an active life position.

Conclusion. Thus, the role and importance of effective digital technologies in the educational process is increasing today, because of the active use of effective technologies in the study of economic sciences in the higher education system by students in their independent and collective activities. only possible if incentives are available. The main purpose of using effective digital technologies in the study of economic sciences is to prepare a person for life in a constantly changing world.

References:

- [1] Ahn, S., & Hemmings, P. (2000). Policy influences on economic growth in OECD countries: an evaluation of the evidence. OECD Economic Department Working Papers No.246.
- [2] Barro, R. J. (1991). Economic growth in a cross section of countries. Quarterly Journal of Economics, 106(2), 407-433.
- [3] Brynjolfsson, E., Hu, Y., & Smith, M. D. (2003). Consumer Surplus in the Digital Economy: Estimating the Value of Increased Product Variety at Online Booksellers. Management Science, 49(11), 1580-1596.
- [4] Corrado, C., Haskel, J., Jona-Lasinio, C., & Iommi, M. (2012). Intangible Capital and Growth in Advanced Economies: Measurement Methods and Comparative Results. IZA Discussion Paper No.6733.
- [5] Czernich, N., Falck, O., Kretschmer, T., & Woessmann, L. (2011). Broadband Infrastructure and Economic Growth. Economic Journal, 121(552)
- [6] Jones, B. F. (2014). The human capital stock: a generalized approach. American Economic Review, 104(11), 3752-3777.
- [7] Mankiw, G., Romer, D., & Weil, D. (1992). A contribution to the empirics of economic growth. The quarterly journal of economics, 107, 407-437.
- [8] OECD. (2014). Measuring the Digital Economy: A New Perspective. OECD Publishing.
- [9] OECD. (2013). Measuring the Internet Economy: A Contribution to the Research Agenda. OECD Digital Economy Papers, No. 226, OECD Publishing.
- [10] OECD. (2012a). ICT investments and productivity: Measuring the contribution of ICTS to growth. OECD.
- [11] OECD. (2012b). ICT skills and Employment: New Competences and Jobs for a Greener and Smarter Economy. OECD Digital Economy Papers, No. 198, OECD publishing.
- [12] OECD. (2001). The driving forces of economic growth: Panel data evidence for the OECD countries.
- [13] Productivity Commission. (2004). ICT Use and Productivity: A Synthesis from Studies of Australia Firms.
- [14] Temple, J. (1999). The new growth evidence. Journal of Economic Literature, 37(1), 112-156

